

Assessment of dispersion patterns for negative stress detection from electroencephalographic signals

Beatriz García-Martínez^{a,b}, Antonio Fernández-Caballero^{a,b,c}, Raúl Alcaraz^d, Arturo Martínez-Rodrigo^{e,f,*}

^a Departamento de Sistemas Informáticos, Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros Industriales, Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha, Albacete, Spain

^b Instituto de Investigación en Informática de Albacete, Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha, Albacete, Spain

^c CIBERSAM (Biomedical Research Networking Centre in Mental Health), Madrid, Spain

^d Research Group in Electronic, Biomedical and Telecommunication Engineering, Escuela Politécnica de Cuenca, Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha, Cuenca, Spain

^e Research Group in Electronic, Biomedical and Telecommunication Engineering, Facultad de Comunicación, Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha, Cuenca, Spain

^f Instituto de Tecnologías Audiovisuales de Castilla-La Mancha, Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha, Cuenca, Spain

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ABSTRACT

Negative stress, or distress, represents a serious problem in advanced societies given its adverse consequences for health. Many studies have focused on the detection of distress from physiological signals such as the electroencephalogram (EEG). To this respect, the combination of regularity-based quadratic sample entropy (QSampEn) and symbolic amplitude-aware permutation entropy (AAPE) has reported valuable outcomes in distress recognition. In the present work, the recently introduced symbolic metric called dispersion entropy (DispEn) is applied for the first time to the same problem. Statistically significant results reported by the single metric have demonstrated its capability for calm and distress detection. Furthermore, relevant differences have been found between the combination of QSampEn with either AAPE or DispEn, finding that the assessment of ordinal and dispersion patterns leads to distinct and complementary outcomes. Finally, the combination of the three entropy metrics has considerably overcome the results ever reported by other indices in similar studies.

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1. Introduction

Negative stress, also called distress, has recently become a major problem in advanced societies because of its high impact on health of people who suffer from it [1]. The economic and social pressure, competitiveness and frenetic rhythm of life in developed countries creates a distressful environment that involves us in a continuous feeling of nervousness and anxiety [2]. Although negative stress is just a *fight or flight* response of our organism for self-protection, a long-term experience of distressful events can lead to serious problems of both physical and mental health. Indeed, different disorders affecting cerebral, immune and endocrine systems could be generated or aggravated as a consequence of negative stress [3]. Therefore, a prompt detection and regulation of

this mental state would help to prevent most of the current health problems [4].

In this sense, it is known that negative stress, as other emotional states, provokes bioelectrical alterations on different physiological systems that can be measured [5]. It is the case of the brain, whose electrical activity is measured by the electroencephalogram (EEG) recording under the scalp. In last years, EEG is receiving growing attention in the emotion recognition field given that the first response against every stimulus is firstly generated in the brain and then spread to other systems [6]. The EEG can hence provide more information than other peripheral recordings that only measure secondary effects of the brain activity [6]. Moreover, the performance of the brain follows nonlinear and nonstationary dynamics even at cellular level, thus the application of nonlinear metrics would be more suitable than traditional linear techniques for the assessment of brain signals [7].

Previous works have already evaluated the performance of some nonlinear entropy metrics when applied to distress and calm detection from EEG signals [8]. It is the case of the sym-

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: arturo.martinez@uclm.es (A. Martínez-Rodrigo).

Fig. 1. Identification of different dispersion patterns (i.e., \mathbf{u}_1 , \mathbf{u}_2 , and \mathbf{u}_3) with similar morphology and ordinal distribution within a time series. The patterns are formed from the quantization levels used for the time series symbolization, i.e., c_1 , c_2 , c_3 and c_4 .

bolic predictability-based metric called amplitude-aware permutation entropy (AAPE), an improved version of permutation entropy (PerEn) index. Although PerEn is a simple and fast metric, considering single ordinal patterns leads to some problems. First, PerEn supposes a continuous distribution of a signal, thus ignoring equal and rare values. However, when analyzing digitized series with coarse quantization levels, those values should not be ignored [9]. Furthermore, PerEn only analyzes the order of the elements for symbolization of a pattern, hence information about their amplitudes is not considered [10]. Consequently, PerEn may not contemplate relevant information related to the amplitude of brain dynamics that could be essential for emotions recognition with EEG signals [11]. As a solution, AAPE also takes into account the amplitude of the symbols in a pattern for the evaluation of its occurrence probability [11]. This metric, in combination with the regularity-based index called quadratic sample entropy (QSampEn), has reported valuable results for calm and distress recognition in previous studies [12]. Indeed, QSampEn has demonstrated a considerable performance when discerning between both emotional states and applied alone or in combination with other nonlinear indices [13,14].

Recently, another symbolic index called dispersion entropy (DispEn) has been introduced [15]. Thus, DispEn estimates the uncertainty of a signal by computing the regularity of patterns with similar values of amplitude dispersion. These patterns are obtained by quantizing the original time series into a specific set of levels, thus reducing the assessment of dynamics of a series to a distribution of amplitude-based symbolic sequences [16]. For instance, Figure 1 shows that patterns are formed from the series of quantization levels assigned to each sample, such that the patterns \mathbf{u}_1 , \mathbf{u}_2 and \mathbf{u}_3 are turned into the sequences $\{c_1, c_3, c_2, c_4\}$, $\{c_1, c_3, c_2, c_4\}$ and $\{c_1, c_2, c_2, c_3\}$, respectively. Although the three patterns exhibit the same morphology and ordinal distribution, amplitude dispersion among samples is different for the pair $(\mathbf{u}_1, \mathbf{u}_2)$ and \mathbf{u}_3 . Indeed, whereas \mathbf{u}_1 and \mathbf{u}_2 present the same dispersion pattern with samples in the four quantization levels, \mathbf{u}_3 shows less dispersion with a distribution in three levels. Hence, the main difference between AAPE and DispEn is the assessment of either permutation or dispersion patterns, such that whereas AAPE considers the amplitude of the samples in a time series to order points into each permutation pattern, DispEn uses this amplitude to estimate dispersion among points within each pattern [16].

The aim of the present work is to evaluate the performance of DispEn for identification of calm and distress from the EEG recording. First, the performance of DispEn will be assessed in terms of

statistical significance of each brain region when discerning between calm and distress. On the other hand, DispEn will be combined with QSampEn with the aim of evaluating the degree of improvement of this new index with respect to the symbolic metric AAPE in combination with the same regularity-based metric. In this way, it will be analyzed whether the newly introduced measure is also able to automatically recognize calm and distress and improve information revealed by metrics used in previous studies. Finally, QSampEn, AAPE and DispEn will be calculated together to discern between the two emotional states, in order to test the complementarity between a regularity-based and two symbolic indices.

This manuscript is structured as follows. Section 2 describes the database and the preprocessing approach, together with mathematical definition of DispEn, and the statistical analyses and classification approaches conducted. Then, results obtained are presented and discussed in Section 3. Final conclusions of this study are summarized in Section 4.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Database description

For this work, EEG recordings were extracted from a publicly available dataset, called Database for Emotion Analysis using Physiological Signals (DEAP) [17]. It contains a total of 1280 trials from 32 participants during the visualization of 40 one-minute length videoclips with emotional content. During the experiment, 32 EEG channels and other peripheral variables were acquired. Furthermore, the emotional state of participants after each visualization was also documented by means of self-assessment manikins (SAM), which is a graphical representation of nine intensity levels of different emotional dimensions. More precisely, two emotional dimensions evaluated by the participants of the experiment were valence (i.e., pleasantness or unpleasantness of a stimulus) and arousal (i.e., activation or deactivation produced by a stimulus). The Cartesian representation of both dimensions is the circumplex model of emotions, which was proposed by Russell [18].

Although the whole valence-arousal space was covered in the DEAP database, only a subset of samples was chosen for the present study. Thus, samples included in distress group were rated with values of arousal higher than 5 and values of valence lower than 3. With respect to the group of control, calm samples had values of arousal lower than 4 and values of valence between 4 and 6. These limit values of valence and arousal were chosen in accordance with previous works also dealing with calm and distress

detection [12,13]. As a result, a total of 122 samples of distress and 137 of calm were finally assessed.

2.2. Preprocessing of EEG recordings

Raw EEG recordings often contain nuisance and interferences that need to be removed before applying further analysis. In this sense, the signals were firstly downsampled from 512 to 128 Hz and referenced to the average potential of all channels. Then, a forward/backward high-pass filtering at 3 Hz and a low-pass filtering at 45 Hz were applied to eliminate baseline and power line interferences. Note that EEG frequency bands involved in emotional processes remained within these cutoff frequencies [19]. Later, a blind source separation technique, called independent component analysis (ICA), was applied to eliminate artifacts that could not be removed in previous preprocessing steps [20]. It is the case of physiological artifacts, such as eye blinks, heart bumps or facial movements, as well as technical artifacts, like electrode pops or bad contact of electrodes on the scalp. It is worth noting that ICA computes independent components from the raw EEG signal and those containing artifacts can be easily identified and rejected, thus maintaining neural information [21]. Finally, highly contaminated channels were eliminated and replaced by the interpolation of adjacent electrodes [22]. Despite having identified these signals before ICA decomposition, interpolation was developed after that step with the aim of avoiding that nonlinearities produced by interpolation influence on the ICA procedure [23]. In this sense, noisy channels did not contribute to the removal of artifactual components [23].

2.3. Dispersion entropy

All points in the original time series $\mathbf{x} = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_N\}$ of length N , are assigned to c classes. For that purpose, the original time series \mathbf{x} is first mapped into $\mathbf{y} = \{y_1, y_2, \dots, y_N\}$ from 1 to c . Among the different mapping options, the authors of this metric recommend the use of a log-sigmoid transfer function [16], defined as:

$$y_j = \frac{1}{1 + e^{\frac{x_j - \mu}{\sigma}}}, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, N, \quad (1)$$

being μ and σ the mean and standard deviation of the signal \mathbf{x} , respectively. After that, a linear algorithm is applied to assign each y_j to an integer ranging from 1 to c . This algorithm is based on expressing each element u_j^c of the mapped signal as $u_j^c = \text{round}(c \cdot y_j + 0.5)$, where $\text{round}()$ represents the rounding operation, either increasing or decreasing a number to the next cipher [15].

Later, each embedding vector $\mathbf{u}_i^{m,c}$ is obtained with embedding dimension m and delay d as $\mathbf{u}_i^{m,c} = \{u_i^c, u_{i+d}^c, \dots, u_{i+(m-1)d}^c\}$, $i = 1, 2, \dots, N - (m-1)d$ [15,24]. After that, each signal $\mathbf{u}_i^{m,c}$ is converted into a dispersion pattern $\pi_{v_0 v_1 \dots v_{m-1}}$, being $u_i^c = v_0$, $u_{i+d}^c = v_1, \dots, u_{i+(m-1)d}^c = v_{m-1}$. The total number of possible dispersion patterns that can be assigned to a vector $\mathbf{u}_i^{m,c}$ is equal to c^m , given that the signal has m elements that can be one of the integers from 1 to c [15]. Thereafter, the relative frequency of each possible dispersion pattern $\pi_{v_0 \dots v_{m-1}}$ of c^m is calculated as

$$p(\pi_{v_0 \dots v_{m-1}}) = \frac{\text{Number}\{i | i \leq N - (m-1)d, \mathbf{u}_i^{m,c} \text{ has type } \pi_{v_0 \dots v_{m-1}}\}}{N - (m-1)d}. \quad (2)$$

Hence, $p(\pi_{v_0 \dots v_{m-1}})$ represents the occurrence rate of each dispersion pattern $\pi_{v_0 \dots v_{m-1}}$ assigned to $\mathbf{u}_i^{m,c}$, divided by the total amount of embedded time series with embedding dimension m .

Finally, DispEn is obtained by means of Shannon entropy:

$$\text{DispEn}(\mathbf{x}, m, c, d) = -\frac{1}{\ln(c^m)} \sum_{\pi=1}^{c^m} p(\pi_{v_0 \dots v_{m-1}}) \cdot \ln(p(\pi_{v_0 \dots v_{m-1}})). \quad (3)$$

Note that the previous equation is normalized by $\ln(c^m)$ to obtain DispEn values between 0 and 1. In this sense, the highest level of DispEn is obtained when all dispersion patterns have the same probability. On the contrary, if the time series is completely regular, only one probability $p(\pi_{v_0 \dots v_{m-1}})$ is different from 0 and thus the minimum value of DispEn is reported [15].

In comparison with other metrics, DispEn does not require a large number of samples in a time series to rise its maximum level with smaller values of m and c . Indeed, the number of points required for obtaining maximum levels of DispEn is $\ln(c^m)$ [15,16]. Nonetheless, although a long signal is not needed to obtain robust estimations of DispEn, the robustness of these estimations increase for a greater number of points in a time series [16].

2.4. Features selection and classification approach

Although each trial had a duration of 60 seconds, only the last 30 seconds were analyzed, as in previous studies [13,17]. These 30 second-length signals were firstly divided into six non-overlapped segments of 5 seconds each ($N = 3840$ samples). Then, DispEn was computed for each segment, thus obtaining the final value as the average of all segments. The selection of appropriate values for the input parameters m and c is essential to ensure a proper calculation of DispEn. Hence, following the recommendations of the authors of this metric, $m = 2$, $c = 6$ and $d = 1$ were selected [16]. Once DispEn was calculated, Shapiro-Wilk and Levene tests were computed to verify normality and homoscedasticity of the distributions obtained for each emotional state. Then, statistical significance at every EEG channel was evaluated by means of a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). It is important to note that only channels with a statistical significance $\rho < 0.05$ were considered as significant.

On the other hand, QSampEn and AAPE were computed similarly dividing the 30 second-length signals into six segments and averaging all partial results to obtain a final value of each entropy for the whole time series. A complete mathematical description of QSampEn and AAPE can be found in [25] and [11], respectively. The values of computation parameters were the same as in a previous study in which these metrics reported promising results in calm and distress recognition from EEG recordings [12]. Thus, QSampEn had a length of vector $m = 2$ and a tolerance $r = 0.25$ times the standard deviation of the data, whereas AAPE was computed with a length $m = 6$.

Moreover, DispEn was combined with QSampEn, in order to compare the results with the similar approach QSampEn+AAPE presented in a previous work [12]. In addition, the three entropy metrics were combined simultaneously in order to verify their complementarity. For that purpose, the performance of QSampEn+AAPE, QSampEn+DispEn and QSampEn+AAPE+DispEn when discerning between calm and distress samples was obtained using a 10-fold cross-validation scheme. It consisted of the random rearrangement of all samples into 10 equally-sized folds, ensuring that all folds contained a representative number of samples from each emotion. After that, the classification model was trained with nine folds and tested with the remaining one. This process was repeated ten iterations, so that a different fold was left in each iteration to test, and the remaining 9 were used to train a support vector machine (SVM) with a Gaussian kernel with a scale of 0.35 and a box constraint of 1.

In each iteration, the performance of the classifier was assessed according to the rate of true positives (TP), true negatives (TN), false positives (FP) and false negatives (FN). More precisely, TP and TN represent the number of samples correctly labelled as positive and negative, respectively, whereas FP and FN are the number of samples incorrectly labelled as positive or negative, respectively. In this case, stress samples corresponded to the positive class, and calm samples were the negative class. These rates were used for the computation of different performance indices. For instance, sensitivity (Se) and specificity (Sp) were the total number of positives or negatives, respectively, correctly identified. On the other hand, classification accuracy (Acc) represented the total amount of samples correctly identified. Moreover, positive predictive value (PPV) was the rate of true positives over the total number of samples labelled as positive. Similarly, negative predictive value (NPV) represented the amount of true negative samples with respect to the total number of negative labels. In addition, the representation of Se against $1-Sp$ at different thresholds was the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve. The area under the ROC curve (AUC) represented the capability of the model to discern between positive and negative classes, assigning higher values for better discriminatory models. Finally, the equal error rate (EER) was obtained at the threshold for which $Se = 1-Sp$, representing the point for which the difference between false acceptance and false rejection of the model was minimum. The lower the level of EER, the better the performance of the classification approach.

In order to provide a clear representation of the methodological procedure followed in the present study, Figure 2 shows a flowchart with detailed information of the proceeding for calm and distress recognition with DispEn, QSampEn and AAPE. Note that section "Classification approach" is the point of the process in which the metrics that are going to be combined are selected (QSampEn+AAPE, QSampEn+DispEn, or QSampEn+AAPE+DispEn). The previous steps in the process are common to all combination approaches.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Statistical analysis

An ANOVA analysis of DispEn performance reported statistically significant differences for a total of 19 out of 32 EEG channels. It is interesting to note that all were located in frontal, central and parietal locations of both brain hemispheres. However, channels in right frontal and left parietal areas reported the largest statistical significance: P3 ($\rho=2.49 \times 10^{-5}$), CP1 ($\rho=2.82 \times 10^{-5}$), FC2 ($\rho=2.90 \times 10^{-5}$), F4 ($\rho=1.20 \times 10^{-4}$), PO3 ($\rho=1.73 \times 10^{-4}$) and Fz ($\rho=3.73 \times 10^{-4}$). Furthermore, Figure 3 shows mean levels of DispEn in all EEG channels for calm and stress conditions. As can be observed, frontal, central and temporal regions of both brain hemispheres and left occipital lobe are the locations exhibiting the highest level of DispEn during calm. In the case of distress, left and right prefrontal channels and left temporal region showed a high level of DispEn, whereas central and posterior brain areas reported lower levels. In addition, the last map shows the difference between mean levels obtained in calm and stress. It should be noted that the highest difference between both emotional states appeared in right frontal and left central and parietal regions. These results were in accordance with the outcomes reported by ANOVA analysis, in which the largest statistical significance was achieved by channels in these locations.

The importance of frontal and parietal brain regions in emotional processes has already been depicted. In this line, the parietal lobe has been associated with the arousal dimension of emotions, whereas frontal areas have been identified with both valence and arousal dimensions [26,27]. In addition, some studies

have reported a synchronized behavior between frontal and parietal areas in calm and distressful conditions. For example, it has been verified that the activation of frontal lobe in one hemisphere is balanced by the activation of the parietal lobe in the other hemisphere [28]. Similar outcomes have been obtained with patients of various mental diseases during meditation sessions [29]. Moreover, symbolic metrics such as AAPE [12], conditional entropy (CE) [30] or permutation min-entropy (PME) [31] applied in previous studies provided results similar to DispEn in terms of the relevance of each brain lobe in emotional states of calm and distress, being the right frontal and left parietal areas those that presented the strongest differences between both emotions. This could be the consequence of the existence of anatomical cortico-cortical connections between those brain regions [32].

On the other hand, it should also be noticed in Figure 3 that the mean levels of DispEn are generally higher for calm states than for distressful conditions in all EEG channels. In other words, the brain dynamics in calm state are more complex than for distress. This outcome has also been described in previous studies. For instance, the correlation dimension (CD) of calm participants presented higher values than for distressed subjects [33]. Similarly, a reduction of relative power in individuals under distressful conditions has also been reported [34]. Furthermore, symbolic indices such as AAPE [12], CE [30], or PME [31] have also presented higher mean values for calm than for distress emotional states. Such decrease of complexity in distress could be explained by a lower ability of the brain to adapt its response to external changes and manage information from the environment, even increasing the probability of suffering from a pathological situation [35].

3.2. Combination of metrics

As aforementioned, the most relevant brain areas highlighted by DispEn were quite similar to those reported by AAPE in previous works [12]. More precisely, channels located in right frontal and left parietal areas were the most significant in both cases. This was predictable given the similarities in the mathematical basis of these two symbolic entropy metrics. Nevertheless, the different symbolization procedures for AAPE and DispEn may also provide different information and then influence on their capability to detect calm and distress emotional states. In order to corroborate this hypothesis, the experiment QSampEn+AAPE presented in a previous study [12] has been replicated with QSampEn+DispEn, with the aim of testing the discrepancies in results obtained when two different symbolic entropies are combined with the same regularity-based entropy metric. In that previous study, only two channels, QSampEn from P4 and AAPE from P3, were combined using an SVM classifier. These two channels were the most statistically significant for each metric when discerning between calm and distress. In the same manner, in the present study DispEn from the left parietal channel P3, the most statistically significant, was combined with QSampEn from the right parietal P4 in an SVM classification approach.

The results obtained for the different performance parameters computed can be found in Table 1. In both cases, i.e., QSampEn+AAPE and QSampEn+DispEn, the classification accuracy was around 80%, more precisely 80.69% for QSampEn+AAPE and 80.31% for QSampEn+DispEn. Hence, the performance of both AAPE and DispEn may seem analogous when combined with QSampEn for calm and distress recognition. Nevertheless, a thorough analysis of the classification results revealed that the capability of deciding whether an emotional sample belonged to either calm or distress group was different for AAPE and DispEn. In the case of QSampEn+AAPE, values of Se and Sp were 71.31% and 89.05%, respectively. In other words, 89.05% of calm samples were correctly identified, whereas the rate of distress samples properly labelled as dis-

Fig. 2. Flowchart with detailed information of the procedure followed in this study.

Fig. 3. Representation of mean level of DispEn for all EEG channels in calm and stress conditions, and the difference between both emotional states.

Table 1
Results of different performance indices computed for the three combination approaches in this study.

Combination Approach	Acc (%)	Se (%)	Sp (%)	AUC (%)	PPV (%)	NPV (%)	EER (%)
QSmpEn + AAPE	80.69	71.31	89.05	89.47	85.29	77.71	18.98
QSmpEn + DispEn	80.31	81.15	79.56	90.34	77.95	82.58	18.98
QSmpEn + AAPE + DispEn	92.28	90.16	94.16	97.64	93.22	91.49	8.03

stress was 71.31%. On the other hand, the combination of QSampEn and DispEn presented values of Se and Sp of 81.15% and 79.56%, respectively. Hence, QSampEn+DispEn model accurately classified 79.56% of calm samples and 81.15% of distress samples. Therefore, despite reaching similar classification accuracy values, the QSampEn+AAPE model might be more sensitive for calm detection, while QSampEn+DispEn showed a better performance in distress recognition. On the other hand, PPV was higher than NPV in the case of QSampEn+AAPE (85.29% and 77.71%, respectively), whereas the contrary occurred for QSampEn+DispEn model (PPV was 77.95% and NPV was 82.58%). In addition, the results of Se and Sp, and also PPV and NPV, were more balanced in the case of QSampEn+DispEn. Finally, the AUC was quite similar for both models, with a difference of less than 1% (89.47% for QSampEn+AAPE and 90.34% for QSampEn+DispEn), and the same value of EER was achieved for both combinations of metrics (18.98%).

According to these outcomes, the selection of either one combination of metrics or the other may depend on the application for which this methodology is going to be used. In real life situations, an accurate and prompt detection of distress may be essential for a proper decision-making process that would or would not allow a person to continue with a determined activity. For instance, it could be the case of an advanced driving assist system for distress detection that would require a distressed driver to stop until calming down in order to avoid risky driving episodes [4]. Similar approaches have been applied in office environments [1], construction field [36] or surgical procedures [37], among others. In such circumstances, the analysis of amplitude dispersion patterns in combination with QSampEn would report a better performance than ordinal patterns and QSampEn.

These differences may be consequence of the mathematical variations between the symbolization procedure of AAPE and DispEn. Concretely, AAPE analyzes the amplitude order of samples in a pattern, whereas DispEn evaluates amplitude dispersion among the samples forming each pattern. Furthermore, the symbolization of equal values in an embedded vector is processed differently with each metric. In the case of AAPE, equalities are ranked according to their order of emergence [15]. As a result, this index is highly sensitive to noise, given that small variations of amplitude could produce a change of the order relations between amplitudes of equal samples in the embedded vector [16]. Conversely, dispersion patterns consider the existence of equal values in an embedding vector, and map data into a reduced number of classes so that close amplitudes are assigned to the same class [15]. Hence, small variations in amplitude would probably not lead to an alteration of the index of the class, making DispEn insensitive to noise [16].

From a neurological perspective, the performance of the brain under calm and distress seems different in terms of the type of dynamics prominent in each emotional state. Given that calm samples are more accurately identified with the combination of QSampEn+AAPE, it could be suggested that the brain activity under calm conditions presents dynamics that are better described with ordinal patterns. On the other hand, the same EEG channels report dynamics in distress situations with a behaviour that could be better adjusted to amplitude dispersion patterns. In other words, depending on the emotional state, determined brain regions show differ-

ent levels of activity and also different types of dynamics more accurately interpretable with either ordinal or dispersion patterns. However, note that it can only be stated for left parietal region, precisely channel P3, which is the only channel from AAPE and DispEn that has been introduced in the classification scheme.

Given that AAPE and DispEn have demonstrated to explain different cases, a new classification scheme was conducted for the combination of QSampEn, AAPE and DispEn simultaneously, in order to corroborate the complementarity of the information reported by each symbolic metric. Precisely, QSampEn from right parietal channel P4 and AAPE and DispEn from left parietal P3 were included as input features in the same SVM-based model used in the previous analysis. As can be observed in Table 1, this classification approach reached an accuracy of 92.28%, which represents an improvement of more than 10% with respect to the combination of QSampEn with only one of the two symbolic entropy indices. In addition, the QSampEn+AAPE+DispEn model was able to correctly identify the 90.16% of distress samples and the 94.16% of calm episodes (values of Se and Sp, respectively), thus overcoming the outcomes derived from the two combinations presented in the previous analyses. This improvement is especially interesting in the rate of distress samples correctly recognized, given that 71.31% and 81.15% of these samples were properly identified with QSampEn+AAPE and QSampEn+DispEn models, respectively. Moreover, PPV and NPV also present a considerable increase with respect to the results obtained in the previous two models. Finally, AUC achieved an increment of more than 7%, and the EER decreased more than 10 percentage points, thus corroborating the improved performance of the combination of the three entropy indices.

Regarding these outcomes, the selection of this triple combination of metrics would be preferable to any previous model of QSampEn and only one symbolic entropy. The number of channels required in each model is the same, given that only two electrodes, QSampEn from right parietal P4 and AAPE and DispEn from left parietal P3, were assessed in all cases. In addition, the computational cost of this triple model is almost the same as in the combinations of two indices. It is due to the fact that the regularity-based QSampEn, which was calculated in all the cases, presents the highest computational cost ($O(N^2)$), whereas AAPE and DispEn are considerably faster ($O(N)$) [16]. Hence, there would not be notable differences in computational costs between calculating QSampEn and either one or both symbolic metrics. These key points, together with the enhancement of the classification performance, makes the combination of QSampEn+AAPE+DispEn the preferable option for calm and distress detection in real life situations.

3.3. Comparison with other works

In the scientific literature, different studies have also focused on calm and distress detection from EEG signals using nonlinear methodologies, as presented in Table 2. Various studies combined different symbolic entropy indices with the regularity-based QSampEn, reaching global classification rates between 75 and 86% [12,14,30]. In the present work, outcomes de-

Table 2

Comparison with the most relevant works dealing with automatic identification of negative stress with EEG recordings and nonlinear metrics.

Work	Experiment	Indices	Classifier	Results
[38]	15 subjects	FD ^b , CD and WEn ^c	LDA ^d and SVM	LDA: 80.1% SVM: 84.9%
[34]	5 EEG channels IAPS ^a 32 subjects 4 EEG channels Videoclips	Statistical features, PSD ^e and HOC ^f	KNN ^g	Stat.: 66.25% PSD: 70.1% HOC: 69.6%
[39]	13 subjects	CD, LZC ^h , LLE ⁱ , PSD	–	Higher complexity in stress
[13]	3 EEG channels Eyes closed 32 subjects 32 EEG channels Videoclips	SampEn, QSampEn and DE ^j	Decision tree	QSampEn + DE: 75.29%
[12]	32 subjects 32 EEG channels Videoclips	QSampEn, PerEn and AAPE	SVM	QSampEn + AAPE: 81.31%
[30]	32 subjects 32 EEG channels Videoclips	QSampEn, CE and CCE ^k	SVM	QSampEn + CCE: 80.31%
[14]	32 subjects	CMQSampEn ^l and CMAAPE ^m	SVM	CMQSampEn + CMAAPE: 86.35%
[31]	32 EEG channels Videoclips 32 subjects	Curve parameters, DPE and PME	KNN	Curve + DPE + PME: 92.32%
Present	32 EEG channels Videoclips 32 subjects 32 EEG channels Videoclips	QSampEn, AAPE and DispEn	SVM	QSampEn+DispEn: 80.31% QSampEn+AAPE+DispEn: 92.28%

^a IAPS: International Affective Picture System^b FD: Fractal dimension^c WEn: Wavelet entropy^d LDA: Linear discriminant analysis^e PSD: Power spectral density^f HOC: High-order crossings^g KNN: K-nearest neighbor^h LZC: Lempel-Ziv complexityⁱ LLE: Largest Lyapunov exponent^j DE: Distribution entropy^k CCE: Corrected conditional entropy^l CMQSampEn: Composite multiscale QSampEn^m CMAAPE: Composite multiscale AAPE

rived from the combination of QSampEn and DispEn were comparable with the aforementioned studies, and the combination of QSampEn+AAPE+DispEn notably overcame these classification results (Acc=92.28%). Indeed, this last accuracy result represents the highest quantitative increase with respect to all studies previously developed in this research line.

In the case of [31], classification results were quite similar to those presented in this manuscript by the combination of QSampEn+AAPE+DispEn. However, not only nonlinear indices were computed in that case. In fact, the classification accuracy was obtained as a combination of various curve-related parameters and different time-lags from two symbolic entropy metrics, namely PME and delayed permutation entropy (DPE). Therefore, the number of parameters needed for the calculation of those curves was also notably higher than in the present work, where only three entropy metrics from two channels have reported similar accuracy outcomes.

In addition, other types of nonlinear methodologies have also been calculated for calm and distress recognition, reporting classification accuracies around 70–80% [34,38,39], as can be observed in Table 2. In this sense, the present work notably improves the results obtained with other nonlinear metrics and other classification models. Furthermore, this study presents a valuable advantage in comparison with the cited works. Other researches introduced

several input features in advanced classifiers to achieve high classification rates, with the inconvenient of obtaining a model that cannot be interpreted from a clinical perspective. On the contrary, the present work follows a classification procedure with a reduced number of input features previously selected, hence it becomes possible to provide a clinical interpretation of the results. Moreover, the technical simplicity of this proposal (only two electrodes would be necessary for calm and distress detection) and its low computational cost makes it adequate for its implementation in real-time applications.

4. Conclusions

The assessment of dispersion patterns by means of DispEn has been applied for the first time to discern between calm and distress emotional states from EEG recordings. To this respect, the relevance of frontal and parietal brain regions in emotional processes has been highlighted, reinforcing findings reported in previous studies. More precisely, right frontal and left parietal areas turned out to be essential for detection of distress and calm conditions, thus presenting the highest differences of DispEn between both emotions. Additionally, although both symbolic metrics AAPE and DispEn have reported similar accuracy outcomes in combina-

tion with QSampEn, the assessment of other performance parameters revealed that analysis of amplitude dispersion patterns allowed a better identification of distress samples, whereas analysis of ordinal patterns provided better recognition of calm samples. Finally, the classification model combining the three entropy metrics reported an accuracy over 92% with only two EEG electrodes, thus overcoming the results reported by all similar works previously developed and turning this model into a promising tool for the recognition of calm and distress emotional states in real life applications.

Finally, some limitations should be considered. First, the DEAP database was not specifically created for calm and distress recognition. Indeed, the whole valence-arousal space was covered during the DEAP experiment. Furthermore, the duration of the audiovisual stimuli was 1 minute for each videoclip, which is too much time for just eliciting one single emotional state. In fact, several emotions could be elicited in each trial, thus being it difficult for participants to properly rate their levels of arousal and valence. On the other hand, although the DEAP database contains various physiological signals, only EEG recordings were evaluated, discarding the possible information that other variables could add to the final results. For this reason, EEG and peripheral variables will be combined in future studies to corroborate the relationship between different physiological systems. Moreover, it would be interesting to use other types of stimuli apart from audiovisual, given that it is not clear which is the best manner of eliciting emotions [5]. To this respect, images, sounds and other stimuli will be tested in future works. Finally, the considered subset of data included 122 samples of distress and 137 of calm from only 32 subjects, which could not be a sufficiently large dataset for accurately determining the robustness and universality of this study. Consequently, in future works the size of the dataset could be increased to verify if these outcomes are representative of the whole population.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Beatriz García-Martínez received her Bachelor and Master degrees in Telecommunications Engineering from Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha in 2016 and 2017, respectively. Currently she is working towards her Ph.D. in Advanced Computer Science Technologies at Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha. Her research interests include Biomedical Signal Processing, Affective Computing and Artificial Intelligence.

Antonio Fernández-Caballero received his M.Sc. in Computer Science from Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, in 1993, and Ph.D. in Artificial Intelligence from Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia in 2001. He is Full Professor at Universidad

de Castilla-La Mancha. His research interests are in Pattern Recognition, Virtual Reality and Affective Computing.

Raúl Alcaraz received his M.Sc. Degree in Electronics Engineering from Universidad de Alcalá de Henares in 2005, and his Ph.D. in Electronic Engineering from Universitat Politècnica de Valencia in 2008. He is Associate Professor at Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha. His research interests mainly include Biomedical Signal Processing.

Arturo Martínez-Rodrigo received his M.Sc. Degree in Telecommunications Engineering from Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha in 2010, and his Ph.D. in Medical Care Research from Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha in 2013. He is Assistant Lecturer at Universidad de Castilla-La Mancha. His research interests include Biomedical Signal Processing and Artificial Intelligence.